

Conceptual replication that the general evaluability theory predicts the cheerleader effect

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A recent article demonstrated that a change in evaluation mode predicts the cheerleader effect (Messner, Carnelli & Höhener 2020). The present article is a conceptual replication, and it provides additional evidence with morphed faces. Again, faces of low attractiveness appear as more attractive when they are flanked by equally low attractive faces than they do in isolation. This is in line with the predictions of the change in evaluation mode, but not with other theoretical explanations of the cheerleader effect (Messner, Carnelli and Höhener, 2020). This article is documentation of this additional study, the data and material. There is no additional theoretical gain, except the evidence that the results could be replicated with morphed faces. For a review of the theoretical explanations of the cheerleader effect, see Messner, Carnelli and Höhener, 2020. Figure 1 gives an overview of the predictions of four theoretical explanations of the cheerleader effect and the manipulation of this study.

Figure 1: Predictions of change in attractiveness of a target face

Targets	Low attractiveness		High attractiveness	
Flankers	Equally low attractive	High attractive	Low attractive	Equally high attractive
<i>Increasing symmetry by averaging</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>Hierarchical encoding</i>	=	+	-	=
<i>Contrast effects</i>	=	-	+	=
<i>Change in evaluation mode</i>	+	-	+	-

Method

Participants

In the study, the participants resided in the United States and were contacted via MTurk. A total of 601 participants completed the study, with 13 failing to pass an attention check and being dismissed. Of the remaining 588 participants, 301 were female, 285 were male, and two identified as other. The mean age was 35.86 ($SD = 10.98$, $range = 18$ to 75).

Sample size

Because some studies have replicated the cheerleader effect (Carragher, Lawrence, Thomas, & Nicholls, 2018; Carragher, Thomas, Gwinn, & Nicholls, 2019; Ying, Burns, Lin, & Xu, 2019), while others failed to do so (van Osch, Blanken, Meijs, & van Wolferen, 2015), it is hardly possible to estimate the effect size. We therefore chose a large sample size.

Design

The study used a 3 (Flankers) \times 2 (Targets' attractiveness) between-subjects design. One-third of the participants only saw the target persons, one-third saw the targets flanked by two highly attractive people, and one-third saw the targets flanked by two people of low attractiveness. We also manipulated the targets' attractiveness: half of the participants were shown only highly attractive targets while the other half were shown only targets of low attractiveness. The condition assignment was random.

We counterbalanced the order in which the faces appeared in addition to the side on which the flankers were presented.

Procedure and Materials

Dependent Variable. After participants gave their informed consent, they were instructed to rate the attractiveness of the face in the middle of the screen on a scale from 0 (not at all attractive) to 100 (extremely attractive). The participants rated two faces. The mean attractiveness rating served as the dependent variable.

The participants rated the attractiveness of two computer-generated faces on a scale from 0 (not at all attractive) to 100 (extremely attractive). The faces were computer-generated by extrapolating the dimension of attractiveness (Todorov & Oosterhof, 2011), and were then validated (Todorov, Dotsch, Porter, Oosterhof, & Falvello, 2013). We selected two sets of faces, each consisting of one target of low attractiveness, two flankers of low attractiveness, one highly attractive target, and two highly attractive flankers.

Data availability. The material and the data are available at

→ [neuen Link auf osf erstellen](#).

Attention check. Typically, online experiments contain an attention check to filter out participants who do not read the instructions carefully. After measuring the dependent variable, participants were shown a picture of a dog's face and were instructed to click on a scale from 0 to 100 within the range of 20 to 30. This served as an attention check.

Ethical approval statement. The study was carried out in accordance with the recommendation of the Federal Act on Research involving Human Beings of the Swiss Confederation. The studies were approved by the ethics committee of the Faculty of Business, Economics and Social Science of the University of Bern.

Results

All the reported results are based on two-sided tests. A between-subjects analysis of variance (ANOVA) showed that the target faces' attractiveness was influenced by the flankers, $F(2, 582) = 6.67, p < .001, \eta^2 = 0.02$. The faces were perceived as more attractive when flanked by faces of low attractiveness ($M = 49.98, SD = 21.8$) than when they were not flanked ($M = 43.26, SD = 20.68$), $t = 3.63, p_{turkey} < .001$, and marginally more attractive than when flanked by highly attractive faces ($M = 45.68, SD = 20.49$), $t = 2.24, p_{turkey} = .07$. No cheerleader effect was observed when a target face was flanked by highly attractive faces, and no difference was reported between the perceived attractiveness of faces that were not flanked ($M = 43.26, SD = 20.68$) and that of faces with highly attractive flankers ($M = 45.68, SD = 20.49$), $t < 1, p_{turkey} = .72$. As a result of the manipulation, highly attractive faces were rated as more attractive ($M = 53.69, SD = 20.25$) than faces of low attractiveness ($M = 39.00, SD = 19.44$) $F(1, 582) = 83.47, p < .001, \eta^2 = 0.123$. However, no interaction was observed between the attractiveness of the targets and that of the flankers $F(2, 582) < 1, p = .79, \eta^2 = 0.001$. This indicates that low-level and highly attractive faces benefit equally from being flanked by faces of low attractiveness.

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